

Leveraging Entrepreneurship to Achieve Sustainable Economic Growth in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the role of entrepreneurship in promoting economic development in Nigeria, with a specific focus on the performance and sustainability of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs). The primary objective is to investigate how core entrepreneurial traits, such as creativity, risk-taking, innovation, and responsiveness to opportunities, impact the sustainability of economic development and contribute to national development. A survey and cross-sectional method approach was employed, combining both qualitative and quantitative methods. Primary data were gathered through structured questionnaires and analysed using descriptive statistics and inferential techniques to determine the relationships between entrepreneurship and economic development. The findings reveal that entrepreneurship plays a crucial role in driving economic development, creating jobs, generating income, and enhancing overall sales performance. However, challenges such as inadequate access to capital, limited government support, and a lack of proper training continue to hinder the performance of SMEs in Nigeria. The study concludes that entrepreneurship is crucial for diversifying the economy beyond oil dependency and that fostering entrepreneurial capacity can drive inclusive growth and innovation. It recommends increased government support through policy implementation, improved access to finance, structured entrepreneurship education, and the creation of an enabling environment to support and sustain entrepreneurial ventures across Nigeria.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Economic Development, Descriptive Statistics

INTRODUCTION

In today's global economy, where technological change, outsourcing, and restructuring dominate business activities, entrepreneurship has emerged as a cornerstone for achieving sustainable development (Muhammed et al., 2025a). It plays a pivotal role in job creation, wealth generation, and long-term economic growth, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria (Juliana et al., 2021). Nigeria, despite its vast natural resources, continues to face multifaceted socio-economic challenges. Entrepreneurship is therefore increasingly recognised as a strategic tool for socio-economic transformation, innovation, and inclusive development. Small and Medium-Scale Enterprises (SMEs) are widely recognised as crucial engines for employment generation, technological advancement, and poverty alleviation (Muhammed et al., 2025b). Entrepreneurs are valued not only for their ability to generate profits but also for their capacity to manage risks and drive economic progress (Adeyinka & Adenike, 2021). However, Nigeria's

entrepreneurial ecosystem faces significant challenges, including poor infrastructure, limited access to finance (Magaji et al., 2023), and regulatory bottlenecks (Awodele, 2022). Addressing these barriers is crucial to harnessing the full potential of entrepreneurship for economic growth.

Entrepreneurship in Nigeria, as in other developing nations, leverages individuals' capacity to create wealth and spur community growth (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2011). Both public and private sector policies aim to support this entrepreneurial drive, with SMEs serving as platforms for employment, technological advancement, and forward linkages with large-scale industries (Magaji et al., 2024). Economic growth can be observed in either quantitative terms, such as increases in output (exports, sales, etc.), or in qualitative terms, including improvements in products and services (Aicha, 2020). Growth is a key metric in evaluating enterprise performance and success (Emeh et al., 2020).

Entrepreneurship is a complex, multidimensional phenomenon studied across various disciplines, including economics, sociology, and management (Magaji et al., 2015). It generally refers to the process of identifying market opportunities and creating value through innovation while taking on financial risks (Omotayo et al., 2024; Emeh et al., 2020). Entrepreneurship development encompasses activities that promote enterprise growth and long-term value creation (Adeoye, 2022). It is a critical factor in driving sales growth, enhancing customer satisfaction, and ultimately determining an enterprise's overall success (Magaji & Saleh, 2010).

According to Agbana & Agbana (2024), key entrepreneurial characteristics, such as risk tolerance, opportunity responsiveness, creativity, and intellectual property, are directly linked to increased sales growth. Risk tolerance fosters innovation and competitive differentiation, and even failed risks can offer valuable business lessons (Magaji, 2004). Opportunity responsiveness enables entrepreneurs to align offerings with market needs, thereby driving growth (Clayton, 2016). Creativity and institutional quality on human development enable entrepreneurs to transform ideas into viable solutions (Magaji, Ismail & Musa, 2025), often resulting in competitive advantages (Adegbola et al., 2021). Intellectual property represents intangible assets that, when correctly managed, enhance market value and profitability (Ibojo, 2015). With Nigeria's unemployment rate estimated at 33% in 2022 and over half of university graduates jobless, entrepreneurship is increasingly seen as a viable solution to the job crisis (Emeh et al., 2020; Aicha, 2020). However, entrepreneurship in Africa, particularly Nigeria, faces many hurdles, including overreliance on oil revenue and inadequate investment in sectors like agriculture and SMEs (Ahmed et al., 2024). Without strategic redirection towards these sectors, economic decline may persist.

Despite extensive literature on entrepreneurship and economic development, gaps remain, particularly concerning how entrepreneurial characteristics influence sales growth in Nigeria's North-West, including Kaduna State. While prior studies by Kpelai (2013), Micheal (2013), and Oni (2014) have focused on women entrepreneurs or policy impacts in Southern Nigeria, limited attention has been paid to the general entrepreneurial landscape and its effect on sales growth in Northern regions.

Moreover, existing literature primarily focuses on micro-enterprises or entrepreneurship education, leaving gaps in sectoral focus and variable inclusion. For instance, studies by Bunten (2020), Ssendi (2019), and Ogunade (2019) centre on macroeconomic impacts, rural female entrepreneurs, and general entrepreneurial development. In contrast, this study uniquely focuses on medium-scale enterprises in Kaduna metropolis, using risk tolerance, opportunity responsiveness, creativity, and intellectual property as core variables, thereby addressing sectoral, environmental, and conceptual gaps in existing research.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Two fundamental concepts require review in this study: the concept of entrepreneurship and the concept of sustainable economic development.

Entrepreneurship

Historically, the term "entrepreneurship" originates from the French word *entrepreneur*, referring to someone who undertakes production tasks. Over time, various scholars have interpreted entrepreneurship in different ways. Ikeme and Onu (2017) view it as the courageous pursuit of investment opportunities aimed at building profit-driven ventures, while Inegbebor (2017) describes it as the capability to identify, establish, and manage business opportunities successfully. According to Onyebueke and Ochonogo (2016) entrepreneurship entails recognising business opportunities, mobilising resources, and sustaining efforts to exploit those opportunities (Musa et al., 2023). However, their definition, like some others, does not fully address the entrepreneurial roles of job creation and risk-taking. Mkpa (2014) adds that beyond income generation, entrepreneurship is rooted in self-reliance, self-employment, and personal initiative, enabling individuals to become job creators rather than job seekers. Further contributions from Gana (2014) and Timmons (2017) define entrepreneurship as both a mindset and a process. It includes planning, organising resources, solving problems, and developing ventures that meet societal needs. Okon et al. (2025) also link entrepreneurship with vocational and technical education, highlighting its role in equipping individuals with practical skills for self-employment and enterprise development, an alignment recognised in Nigeria's National Policy on Education. Ultimately, this study adopts the view of Hisrich and Peters (2012), who define entrepreneurship as a dynamic process of creating incremental wealth. This view reflects the broader understanding that entrepreneurship is not just about starting businesses, but about innovating, taking risks, solving problems, and creating sustainable value for individuals and society as a whole (Ismail et al., 2025).

Economic Development

Economic development can be described as the process through which the economic conditions and quality of life of individuals, communities, or regions are enhanced by effectively utilising resources and enacting policies that support growth, wealth creation, and improved living standards (Musa et al., 2025). It involves intentional efforts to improve the socio-economic well-being of a nation, region, or individual (Ethen, 2016), guided by specific objectives and development targets (John, 2016). According to Boulding and Kine (2013), economic development is primarily a policy-driven initiative aimed at improving people's livelihoods. It entails the transformation of an economy from one with minimal resources and limited options to one that offers increased opportunities and greater access to resources, thereby promoting better living conditions (Ahmed, 2016). As defined by Oliver (2012), economic development entails structural changes in an economy, such as the adoption of modern technologies and mechanisation, which enhance labour productivity, increase income, boost employment levels, and improve the population's standard of living (Adekoya et al., 2025). Dungrit, Bahago, and Gotip (2022) emphasise that economic development is not limited to a single sector but encompasses comprehensive growth across all areas of the economy. It is reflected in sustained increases in real per capita income, institutional strength, human capital advancement, and overall societal well-being. For a nation to achieve proper development, its economic, social, and political institutions must align with global benchmarks, such as the Sustainable Development Goals (Magaji et al., 2025). In the case of Nigeria, Lemo (2013) notes that it is still considered a developing country, facing significant challenges in areas such as wealth creation, education, gender equity, income distribution, job creation, and poverty alleviation. Vinlander (2012) argues that entrepreneurship plays a vital role in economic development not just through starting businesses, but by identifying opportunities, allocating resources effectively, and creating added value that contributes to national growth. Entrepreneurs are often regarded as catalysts for economic change. Lee (2017) describes an entrepreneur as an individual who innovatively combines resources, takes calculated risks, and applies new knowledge to create something novel. As Yeong-NG (2012) highlights, entrepreneurs have been widely recognised for their impactful roles in driving economic growth, fostering development, stimulating innovation, generating employment, and revitalising communities. Thus, economic development is reflected in the increasing value of goods and services produced within an

economy, accompanied by social improvements and institutional resilience (Magaji et al., 2019). While entrepreneurs are celebrated for their visible achievements, their more profound contributions to nation-building and sustained economic transformation are often undervalued.

Theoretical Framework

To underpin this study, Economic Entrepreneurship Theory is used.

Economic Entrepreneurship Theory

Richard Cantillon, an 18th-century economist, is widely credited with laying the groundwork for modern entrepreneurial thought through his pioneering work *Essai sur la Nature du Commerce en Général* (1734). In this work, Cantillon introduced the Economic Entrepreneurship Theory, presenting the economy as a dynamic system influenced heavily by entrepreneurial activity. He described entrepreneurs as essential connectors between the production of goods and their consumption (Hébert & Link, 2009). Unlike later economists who confined entrepreneurship to innovation or large-scale enterprises, Cantillon offered a more inclusive view. He suggested that anyone who engages in economic transactions with uncertain returns, including farmers, merchants, street traders, and even beggars, could be classified as an entrepreneur (Casson, 2003).

At the heart of Cantillon's theory is the entrepreneur's dual function as both a producer and a market participant. Entrepreneurs, according to Cantillon, stimulate economic flow by acquiring inputs at known costs and converting them into finished goods or services sold in unpredictable markets (Blaug, 2000). This naturally exposes them to risk, as their success depends on accurately forecasting consumer demand and navigating price volatility (Audretsch et al., 2015). For example, a restaurant owner fits Cantillon's definition of an entrepreneur, as they must purchase ingredients, hire labour, and manage operational expenses, all while facing uncertainty about customer turnout and sales revenue.

One of the distinguishing features of Cantillon's theory is its broad interpretation of entrepreneurship. By recognising the roles of small-scale and informal actors within the economic system, Cantillon emphasised that entrepreneurship is not limited to elite innovators or large enterprises but is a widespread phenomenon found throughout society (Hébert & Link, 2009). However, this view has also attracted criticism for downplaying the importance of innovation, a perspective later advanced by Joseph Schumpeter (1934), who argued that entrepreneurship fundamentally involves creative disruption and transformative change. Still, Cantillon's emphasis on risk management, resource coordination, and adaptive behaviour continues to shape modern discussions on entrepreneurship, particularly within microeconomic and small business contexts (Blaug, 2000).

Core Contributions of Cantillon's Theory:

1. **Risk and Uncertainty** – Entrepreneurs earn profits by dealing with market unpredictability (Casson, 2003).
2. **Economic Intermediation** – They function as mediators between producers and consumers, facilitating value exchange (Audretsch et al., 2015).
3. **Inclusive Scope** – Cantillon recognised entrepreneurship across formal and informal sectors, including small-scale and self-employed individuals (Hébert & Link, 2009).

Cantillon's redefinition of entrepreneurship shifted the concept from a status of privilege to a universal economic role. For instance, a street vendor buying produce in bulk and selling it at fluctuating prices exemplifies Cantillon's entrepreneur who assumes financial risk and adapts to market demand (Cantillon, 1734, as cited in Blaug, 2000). While Schumpeter (1934) later emphasised innovation as the hallmark of true entrepreneurship, Cantillon's focus on risk, exchange, and adaptability remains remarkably relevant today, especially within gig economies and the informal business sector (Audretsch et al., 2015).

Empirical Review

Onwuka, Nwachuya, Okaforocha, Imoagwu, and Ezeife (2025) investigated the impact of entrepreneurship on Nigeria's economic development, focusing on its implications for job creation, innovation, and wealth generation. Employing a descriptive statistical approach, data from questionnaire responses were analysed to address the research questions. The objectives of the study were threefold: firstly, to assess the relationship between entrepreneurship and job creation and employment, thereby elucidating its effects on the country's economic development; secondly, to identify and analyze the key challenges and barriers encountered by entrepreneurs in Nigeria, and to examine their repercussions on economic growth, innovation, and wealth generation; and finally, to evaluate the impact of the entrepreneurial ecosystem and government policies on the sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures and their influence on Nigeria's economic development. The study recommends that policymakers should prioritise the formulation and implementation of policies that directly support and motivate entrepreneurial activities. These policies should be designed in a manner that encourages entrepreneurship by addressing key challenges and barriers faced by entrepreneurs, such as access to finance, regulatory hurdles, and infrastructure deficiencies.

Jabi and Ishi (2025) examine the impact of entrepreneurship on economic growth and development in Benue State, Nigeria. The research employed a descriptive and cross-sectional survey design, with a sample size of 208 entrepreneurs selected from Benue North-West senatorial district. The results show a significant relationship between economic growth and development, as well as a significant influence of economic growth on entrepreneurship. However, the challenges faced by SMEs and business start-ups have a significant impact on economic development. The study recommends inclusive economic strategies, SME-friendly policies, and infrastructural improvements to create a conducive environment for long-term growth and development. The findings contribute to the existing literature on entrepreneurship and economic development, providing insights for policymakers and stakeholders seeking to promote sustainable development in Benue State and similar regions.

Omotayo, Adewole, Kadirir and Attah (2024) examined the impact of entrepreneurship on economic development in Nigeria. Annual time series data spanning from 1992 to 2022, analysed with ARDL techniques, was employed. The rate of self-employment in the country was used as a proxy for entrepreneurship. The contributions of SMEs, private sector credit, and the inflation rate were also added to the model, while the human development index was used to represent economic development. The results showed that the self-employment rate is positive but insignificant in the short run, while its impact on economic development in the long run is significant. The contribution of SMEs and credit to the private sector is positive but insignificant in the long run, while the impact of the inflation rate is inversely related. This indicates that the government, in conjunction with monetary authorities, should formulate and implement sound economic policies that will enable entrepreneurship to thrive; this should not be done without taking cognisance of macroeconomic variables. More importantly, financial institutions, especially deposit money banks, should be required to support entrepreneurial development by providing start-up funds for entrepreneurs at a reduced or concessionary rate.

Agbana and Agbana (2024) delve into the intricate dynamics of entrepreneurship development and its profound impact on the nation's economic landscape. Highlighting the multifaceted facets of entrepreneurship, the research evaluates its role in fostering sustainable economic growth, job creation, and poverty alleviation. By amalgamating insights from diverse scholarly perspectives and empirical data, the study assesses the challenges impeding entrepreneurship in Nigeria. It examines the intersection between entrepreneurship, sustainable development, and societal well-being, highlighting the crucial role of innovative, environmentally conscious practices in promoting long-term progress. The research outlines the essential skills and managerial competencies necessary for effective business management, highlighting the importance of mentorship, networking, and capacity-building initiatives. Statistical analyses and empirical evidence underpin the conclusions, unveiling critical relationships between

entrepreneurship development, economic growth, and the challenges encountered, thereby offering valuable insights and recommendations for policy interventions and future research endeavours.

Krokeyi and Michael (2024) examine the relationship between entrepreneurship and economic development in Nigeria, with a specific focus on the impact of micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) on unemployment and per capita GDP. Using annual time series data from 1981 to 2022, the analysis was conducted employing the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique. The results indicated that government loans to MSMEs and real per capita GDP had a significant and negative impact on the unemployment rate in both the long and short terms. Conversely, the government's external debt was found to have a positive and significant effect on the unemployment rate over the same periods. Additionally, the working-age population had a positive but insignificant impact on the unemployment rate in the long run, while in the short run, this impact was negative and insignificant. Further findings revealed that government loans to MSMEs and the working-age population had a positive and significant influence on real per capita GDP in both the long and short run. On the other hand, the government's external debt and the inflation rate had a negative and insignificant effect on real per capita GDP in both the long and short term. The study suggests that policymakers should prioritise enhancing labour market efficiency by promoting skills development, improving access to education and training, and fostering entrepreneurship, particularly among the working-age population.

Usman and Markus (2024) investigate the role of entrepreneurship skills acquisition in the sustainable development of students in tertiary institutions in Jalingo, Taraba State. The objectives of the study include examining the entrepreneurship skills required by business education students, discussing factors limiting the development of these skills, evaluating their impact on sustainable development, and determining their overall role in fostering student growth. A sample size of 650 students from various tertiary institutions in Jalingo metropolis was surveyed. The findings reveal that key entrepreneurial skills, including financial literacy, communication, and marketing, are essential for achieving sustainable development. However, several factors impede the development of these skills, including a lack of funding, an inadequate curriculum, and insufficient practical training. Despite these barriers, the acquisition of entrepreneurship skills significantly impacts students' sustainable development by enhancing employment opportunities, economic empowerment, innovation, poverty reduction, and community development. The study concludes that entrepreneurship education plays a crucial role in equipping students with the essential skills necessary for sustainable development. It recommends curriculum enhancement, increased resource allocation, faculty development, and improved infrastructure for educational institutions. Additionally, it suggests supportive policies, public-private partnerships, and economic stability measures from the government. For students, active participation, continuous learning, and networking are encouraged. Lastly, community and industry support through mentorship programs is emphasised.

Ayodele and Gata (2024) examined the effect of innovation on the performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Bida, Niger State. The method employed in this study is a descriptive survey, which involves collecting data from respondents through the administration of questionnaires. A total of 355 questionnaires were administered, of which 335 were duly filled out and returned. Therefore, our sample size is 335. The 335 returned questionnaires were analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The results demonstrate a positive but insignificant relationship between product innovation and business performance. Additionally, a positive and significant relationship is found between Process innovation and business performance. Furthermore, a positive and significant relationship is revealed between marketing innovation and business performance. In conclusion, innovation is a crucial factor in driving business performance. Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Bida metropolis had embraced it with 96% of the respondent Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) having at least one innovation. Research findings indicate that product, process, marketing, and innovation had a positive effect on business performance. Process and marketing innovation had a

statistically significant impact on business performance, whereas product innovation had no significant effect on business performance. The study therefore recommends that owners/managers of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) should develop and implement innovations in their firms to improve performance. Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) owners/ managers should consider pursuing an innovation strategy to improve business performance.

Sule (2024) examined the effect of youth entrepreneurship empowerment on economic development in Maiduguri Metropolitan Area, Borno State, Nigeria. This study used a survey research design. Primary data were collected using a self-developed structured questionnaire administered via face-to-face interviews. The population considered for this study includes youth entrepreneurs who were beneficiaries of the youth empowerment program in the Maiduguri Metropolitan Council Area of Borno State, Nigeria. This study employed multi-stage sampling technique to randomly and proportionately select youth entrepreneurs engaged in manufacturing, food & beverages making, agriculture (farming, poultry) and trading (produce marketing) in Maiduguri Metropolitan Council Area A total sample size of 500 youth entrepreneurs that have benefited from the Borno State Government empowerment programme were randomly and proportionately selected from each of the seven (7) wards of Maiduguri Metropolitan Council Area and used for the study. The one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) would be used to analyse the data. The study's findings indicate that Entrepreneurship has contributed significantly to Nigeria's economic development, as it has created more employment opportunities for job seekers.

Carlice and Odiwo (2024) examined how entrepreneurial development affects job creation in Edo state. The primary goal was to assess the impact of entrepreneurial growth on employment generation in Edo State. The study employed a descriptive correlational survey methodology to accomplish its goals and test its hypotheses, as it was necessary to determine the relationship between its variables. Because the researchers were interested in obtaining data directly from the subjects rather than relying solely on previously collected data, they chose to employ a questionnaire as their primary method of data collection. A population of 2,000 small and medium-sized entrepreneurs in Edo State was used for the study. We used the Taro Yamane sample size calculation to determine a sample size of 333. The study was carried out using SPSS version 21 software and employed descriptive, correlational, and regression analytical techniques. The results show that applying the entrepreneurial development constructs of competitive aggressiveness, innovativeness, proactivity, and risk-taking would offer a more realistic approach in lowering Edo State's unemployment rate as well as in efforts to create jobs ($R^2=0.951$ and 0.916 , $P\text{-value} = .000$). Based on the findings, it was recommended that the government should make sure the entrepreneurship education system is redesigned and fully supported to ensure that people are sufficiently informed about the value and benefits of working for themselves by being creative and taking risks.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design used in this study is a cross-sectional survey design. The study employs a cross-sectional research design, as a structured questionnaire was used to collect data from respondents simultaneously. Survey research design was employed in this study because it facilitates the provision of accurate descriptions necessary for informed policy decisions. This study assessed the impact of entrepreneurship on the sustainability of economic development in Nigeria, using registered Small and Medium-Scale Enterprises (SMEs) in Kaduna metropolis. Therefore, a survey research design is necessary for this type of research. A survey enables the collection of data from a large sample over a specific period of time. For this reason, this research obtained information for the study using a survey method, which involved primary data collection through the use of questionnaires.

Population and Sample Size

The Population for this study comprises all registered Small and Medium-Scale Enterprises (SMSEs) owners/managers in Kaduna Metropolis, as of February 2025, registered under the Kaduna State Chambers of Commerce, Industries, Mines, and Agriculture (KADCCIMA), which totals 2,534 SMSEs (KADCCIMA, 2025). This study focused on the owners/managers of SMEs, also known as entrepreneurs in this study, operating within the Kaduna metropolis. This area was chosen for this study because it generates homogeneity of related business sectors in a similar location. The population breakdown is as shown in the table below:

Table 3.1 Sector Population Distribution

Sectors	Total Population
Agriculture	316
Construction/Real Estate	129
Financial Services	159
Health Care	152
ICT	158
Industrial Goods	267
Natural Resource	232
Oil and Gas	236
Services	275
Utilities	217
Conglomerate	173
Consumer Goods	220
Total	2534

Source: KADCCIMA (2025)

Sample of the Study

The Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size determination table was used to determine the sample size for this study. Sample size is approximately 33 for the population of 2534

Proportional allocation was also performed for each stratum using a ratio, thus ensuring that each stratum or sector is appropriately represented.

The Bowley (1926) proportional formula was used, which is given as:

$$n_h = \frac{nxN_h}{N}$$

Where:

N_h = Sample size for stratum h

N_h = Population size for stratum h

N = Total population size

n = computed sample size

This formula was used to compute the number of respondents selected from each sector. Therefore, using the Bowley Proportional formula to get the stratified sample size. The sample size is determined by the total number of the MSEs of each sector divided by the total population of the study and to be multiplied by the sample size gotten from the total population of the study.

Where;

$$n_h = \frac{nx}{N} N_h$$

Table 3.2 Proportional Distribution Table

Agriculture	316/2534*335= 42
Construction/Real Estate	129/2534*335= 17
Financial Services	159/2534*335= 21
Health Care	152/2534*335= 20
ICT	158/2534*335= 21
Industrial Goods	267/2534*335= 35
Natural Resource	232/2534*335= 31
Oil and Gas	236/2534*335= 31
Services	275/2534*335= 36
Utilities	217/2534*335= 29
Conglomerate	173/2534*335= 23
Consumer Goods	220/2534*335= 29
Total	335

Sources and Methods of Data Collection

The source of data for this study is the primary sources while questionnaire was the tool used for the collection of the said data. Abdullahi (2015) agreed “the major advantage of using a questionnaire is that, it can offer a reliable consistent presentation of items”. Questionnaires were drawn and distributed to the respondents. The questionnaire for data collection was adapted from the works of John (2015) and that of Ethen, (2016) for entrepreneurship and economic development respectively.

Techniques of Data Analysis

In order to examine the impact of entrepreneurship characteristics on sales growth in Kaduna, the parametric technique was employed using ordinary least regression analysis, because this analysis is a way of statistically sorting out which of those variables certainly have an impact and it also helps to determine how well the independent variables predict the value of the dependent variable (Garson, 2016). Also, descriptive statistics will check for the characteristics of the data, correlation will check for the relationship and then the regression. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was employed purposely for checking the issues of multicollinearity in the variables.

Reliability and Validity

In this section, the reliability results of the models of the study are presented and interpreted. The reliability and validity test are formulated for the study in order to check the validity and also the level of reliability of the questionnaire used in collecting the data which is being presented in Table 3.4 below;

Table 3.4 Reliability Statistics

Cronbach’s Alpha	Variables
.714	Risk Tolerance
.706	Opportunity Responsiveness
.826	Creativity
.729	Intellectual Property

Source: SPSS 23 (Appendix ii)

The reliability research questionnaire is generally measured using Cronbach’s alpha statistics. It is specifically aimed at measuring the internal consistency of a questionnaire. The greater the degree of consistency and stability in an instrument, the greater is its reliability (Kumar, 2005). Cronbach’s alpha is a consistency test of whether all items within the instrument measure the same thing. Cronbach’s alpha is designed on a scale that ranges from 0 to 1. Although a negative value is possible, such a value indicates a

scale in which some items measure the opposite of what other items measure. The closer the alpha is to 1.00, the greater the internal consistency of items in the research instrument.

Cronbach's alpha indicated that the questionnaire achieved acceptable reliability, with α ranging from 0.706 to 0.826 among all variables. Therefore, Cronbach's alpha with respect to the outcome shows that the questionnaire appears to be worthy of retention, thereby enhancing the validity of the data collected using the questionnaire. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient, which shows a score of over .70 for high internal consistency. In this case, $\alpha = 0.714$ for risk tolerance, 0.706 for opportunity responsiveness, 0.826 for creativity, and 0.729 for intellectual property, which indicates that the questionnaire is reliable.

Model Specification

The models for this study are as follows:

The model is captured from Brady & Cronin's (2011) study on the Hierarchical service quality model, but adapted by the researcher to include;

In functional form:

$$ED = f(ENT) \tag{1}$$

The dependent variable, economic development, is a function of the independent variable, which is **entrepreneurship**.

In equation form, it is represented as follows:

$$ED = \alpha + B_1 RKTL + B_2 OPRP + B_3 CRTY + B_4 ITPT + E_i \tag{2}$$

Where:

ED = Economic development

RKTL = risk tolerance

OPRP = opportunity responsiveness

CRTY = creativity

ITPT = intellectual property

E Standard Error of Estimate

α = Constant or Intercept

B₁ – B₄ Coefficient of independent Variable

Justification for the Technique of Analysis

The technique of analysis is correlation and regression analysis, because correlation analysis is used to explain the relationship between the dependent and independent variables in terms of association. Regression analysis is used to explain the relationship between variables in terms of prediction/causation. Regression is a robust technique used to analyse data, aiding in the decision to either accept or reject a hypothesis. To demonstrate the relationship and impact of the dependent and independent variables, correlation and regression analysis were used in the study.

RESULT AND DATA ANALYSIS

Data Presentation and Analysis

Data analysis was carried out using the statistical tool of SPSS 23. The data analysis shows the distribution of demographic factors and respondents' responses. A total number of 335 questionnaires were administered to the respondents under the study and out of the administered questionnaires 328 were filled and returned. This is 97.91% rate of response.

The percentage returns and response were considered reasonable enough for comprehensive analysis and generalization.

Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics of the data collected for the study is presented and discussed in this section. The summary of the descriptive statistics of the data collected is presented in Table 4.1 as follows;

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

Descriptive Statistics									
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
RKTL	328	1.00	5.00	3.1973	.87592	-.610	.198	-.425	.394
OPRP	328	1.00	5.00	2.1599	.75746	.843	.198	.791	.394
CRTY	328	1.00	5.00	2.6110	.60612	-.081	.198	-.069	.394
ITPT	328	1.00	5.00	2.8147	.80538	-.027	.198	-.688	.394
ED	328	1.00	5.00	2.9627	.86028	1.058	.198	4.903	.394
Valid N (listwise)	328								

Source: SPSS 23

Table 4.1 shows that our measure of economic development (ED) has a minimum value of 1 and 5 as the maximum value, this indicates that 1 is the lowest value in the data set while 5 is the highest value in the data set which signifies that there are no outlier issues in the data set. The average value of the ED is 2.9627 with standard deviation of 0.86028, signifies that the data deviate from both side of the mean value by approximately 0.860. This implies that there is dispersion of the data from the mean, because of the value of standard deviation which is not close to the mean. The skewness value is at 1.058 and the Kurtosis value is at 4.903. Therefore, the descriptive statistics for sales growth reveal that the variable's nature is dispersed from the mean, and as a result, it shows no indication of outliers.

The results from the table also indicate that the minimum and maximum values of the risk tolerance (RKTL) are 1 and 5, respectively, indicating the absence of outlier issues in the dataset. The mean value of 3.1973 and the standard deviation of 0.87592 in the data imply that there is dispersion from the mean value by approximately 0.88. The skewness value is at -0.610, and the Kurtosis value is at -0.425. Therefore, the descriptive statistics for risk tolerance reveal that the variable's nature is dispersed from the mean, and as a result, it shows no indication of outliers.

The results from the table also indicate that the minimum and maximum values of the opportunity responsiveness (OPRP) are 1 and 5, respectively, indicating the absence of outlier issues in the dataset. The mean value of 2.1599 and standard deviation of 0.75746 in the data imply that there is dispersion from the mean value by approximately 0.76. The skewness value is at 0.843, and the Kurtosis value is at 0.791. Therefore, the descriptive statistics for opportunity responsiveness reveal that the variable's nature is dispersed from the mean, and as a result, shows no indication of outliers.

The results from the table also indicate that the minimum and maximum values of creativity (CRTY) are 1 and 5, respectively, indicating the absence of outlier issues in the dataset. The mean value of 2.6110 and the standard deviation of 0.60612 in the data imply that there is dispersion from the mean value by approximately 0.61. The skewness value is at -0.081, and the Kurtosis value is at -0.069. Therefore, the descriptive statistics for creativity reveal that the nature of the variable is dispersed from the mean, and as a result, show no indication of outliers.

The results from the table also indicate that the minimum and maximum values of the intellectual property (ITPT) are 1 and 5, respectively, indicating the absence of outlier issues in the dataset. The mean value of 2.8147 and the standard deviation of 0.80538 in the data imply that there is dispersion from the mean value by approximately 0.81. The skewness value is at -0.027, and the Kurtosis value is at -0.688.

Therefore, the descriptive statistics for intellectual property reveal that the nature of the variable is dispersed from the mean and, as a result, show no indication of outliers.

The result implies that there is no existence of any form of outliers in the variable, which therefore indicates that the variables have no bias in terms of variable selection.

Correlation Matrix

In this section, the result of the Pearson correlation Coefficients of the variables of the study is presented in Table 4.2 as follows;

Table 4.2 Correlation Matrix of the Dependent and Independent Variables

Correlations

		ED	RKTL	OPRP	CRTY	ITPT
ED	Pearson Correlation	1	.585**	.582**	.489**	.610**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	328	328	328	328	328
RKTL	Pearson Correlation	.585**	1	.601**	.490**	.752**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	328	328	328	328	328
OPRP	Pearson Correlation	.582**	.601**	1	.494**	.604**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	328	328	328	328	328
CRTY	Pearson Correlation	.489**	.490**	.494**	1	.571**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	328	328	328	328	328
ITPT	Pearson Correlation	.610**	.752**	.604**	.571**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	328	328	328	328	328

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS 23 (Appendix II)

The correlation matrix is used to determine the degree of association between independent variables and the dependent variable. It is also used to identify whether there is a relationship between independent variables themselves, to detect the possibility of multicollinearity amongst the explanatory variables. This is necessary so that a broader picture than we could have obtained when regressed separately against performance would be obtained.

In the correlation matrix, which reflects the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variables. It shows that economic development (ED) has a positive relationship with risk tolerance (RKTL), as denoted by the value 0.585, which indicates that (RKTL) has a moderate and positive relationship with (ED). Opportunity responsiveness (OPRP) exhibits a positive relationship with economic development (ED), with a correlation coefficient of 0.582, indicating a moderate and positive association between OPRP and ED. Creativity (CRTY) has a moderate positive relationship with economic development (ED), with a value of 0.489. At the same time, intellectual property (ITPT) has a strong and positive relationship with economic development (ED), with a value of 0.610.

In the correlation matrix that reflects the relationship between the independent variables and themselves. (CRTY) has a moderate positive relationship with (RKTL) with a value of 0.490, while (CRTY) has a moderate and positive relationship with (OPRP) with a value of 0.494. (ITPT) has a strong and positive relationship with (RKTL) with a value of 0.752; (ITPT) has a strong and positive relationship with (OPRP) with a value of 0.604; (ITPT) has a moderate and positive relationship with (CRTY) with a value of 0.571. While (RKTL) has a strong and positive relationship with (OPRP), with a value of 0.601.

According to Gujarati and Porter (2009), a correlation coefficient between two independent variables

above 0.10 is considered excessive and may indicate the existence of multicollinearity. From Table 4.2, all correlation coefficients between pairs of independent variables are less than 0.10. Hence, suggesting that the four independent variables can be well fitted into a regression model. The result implies that there is a multi-correlation among the independent variables, and the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable is significant, indicating that there is no form of multicollinearity within the independent variables.

Summary of Regression Results

In this section, the regression results of the study's models are presented and interpreted. The hypotheses formulated for the study are also tested from the results as presented in Table 4.3 below.

Table 4.3 Summary of Regression Result

Variables	Co-efficient	t-values	p-values
Coefficient	0.532	2.146	0.034
RKTL	0.281	2.925	0.046
OPRP	0.297	3.241	0.031
CRTY	0.292	2.786	0.026
ITPT	0.252	3.354	0.020
R	0.686		
R ²	0.470		
Adjusted R ²	0.456		
F-stat	32.166		
F-sig			0.05

Source: SPSS 23 (Appendix II)

Entrepreneurship Characteristics and Sales Growth

The results from Table 4.3 indicate that risk tolerance, opportunity responsiveness, creativity, and intellectual property have a significant impact on sales growth at the 5% level of significance, respectively.

Cumulatively, the R² (0.470), which is the combined coefficient of determination, indicates the extent to which the independent variables explain the total variation in the dependent variable. The remaining 53% is attributed to other factors not accounted for by the model used in this study. Thus, it signifies that 47% of the total variation in economic development in Nigeria, as observed in registered SMEs in Kaduna metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria, is attributed to risk tolerance, opportunity responsiveness, creativity, and intellectual property. This indicates that the explanatory variables are well selected and combined, as the R-squared value is positive and satisfies the minimum rule of thumb, which is 25% (Sao, 2010).

The F-statistic of 32.166, which is significant at the 5% level of significance, indicates that the model of the study is a good fit. The value of the F-statistic, which is statistically significant at a 5% level of significance (p < 0.05), indicates that there is a 95% probability of confidence that the association among the study variables is not due to chance.

DISCUSSION OF MAJOR FINDINGS

The analysis reveals compelling evidence that entrepreneurial factors have a significant influence on economic development in Nigeria, as demonstrated by SMEs in Kaduna Metropolis. Each of the four hypotheses tested yielded statistically significant results, rejecting the null assumptions and highlighting the critical role of entrepreneurial behaviour in sustaining economic growth.

Risk Tolerance and Economic Development

The study found that risk tolerance positively impacts economic development, with a significant t-value (2.925) and p-value (0.046). This suggests that SMEs willing to take calculated risks, such as investing in

innovation or expanding into new markets, contribute more substantially to economic progress. This aligns with Schumpeter's theory of entrepreneurship, which posits that risk-taking drives innovation and long-term growth. In Nigeria's challenging business environment, SMEs that navigate risks effectively help sustain employment and productivity, reinforcing the need for policies that support risk mitigation, such as access to credit and business insurance.

Therefore, this result is consistent with the findings of (Bakar & Zainol, 2015) That risk tolerance had a significant effect on sales growth. Eniola and Entebang, (2020) Found a significant relationship between risk tolerance and sales growth. Otika and Ireneus, (2019) Found a significant relationship between Risk tolerance and sales growth. Specifically, in the context of Nigeria, Onyenma and Mark (2020) also found that Risk tolerance significantly predicts the sales growth of entrepreneurs.

Opportunity Responsiveness and Economic Development

Opportunity responsiveness also showed a strong positive relationship with economic development (t-value = 3.241, p-value = 0.031). SMEs that quickly identify and capitalise on market opportunities, such as emerging consumer demands or technological advancements, enhance competitiveness and stimulate economic activity. This finding supports Kirzner's theory of entrepreneurial alertness, emphasising how agility in seizing opportunities fosters market efficiency and growth. For Nigeria, improving market information systems and reducing bureaucratic barriers could further enhance the responsiveness of SMEs. There is literature supporting the significant positive relationship between opportunity responsiveness and economic development in Nigeria (Onyenma & Mark, 2020; Onyenma, Tamunomiebi & Mark, 2020)

Creativity and Economic Development

Creativity emerged as another significant driver (t-value = 2.786, p-value = 0.026), indicating that innovative SMEs, through unique products, services, or business models, play a vital role in economic diversification. This echoes endogenous growth theory, which links innovation to sustained development. In Nigeria, where reliance on oil has stifled diversification, fostering creativity through R&D incentives and startup incubators could unlock new economic pathways. Empirically, the significant positive relationship between creativity and economic development is consistent with the findings of previous studies (Islami, Mustapha, & Marija, 2020; Goshu & Kitaw, 2017).

Intellectual Property and Economic Development

Intellectual property (IP) protection was also positively associated with development (t-value = 3.354, p-value = 0.020). SMEs that secure IP rights benefit from increased investment, innovation, and competitive advantage. Weak IP enforcement in Nigeria has long deterred innovation; strengthening legal frameworks and raising awareness about IP rights could thus spur SME growth and attract foreign investment.

The result also supports the findings of Otika and Ireneus (2019), Kenneth (2015), Abubakar and Abubakar (2015) that reported a significant positive association between intellectual property and economic growth and development, but contradicts the findings of Olaniyi and Olu (2015) Mojekeh, Nwokolie and Okwurawe (2018) who found no significant relationship between intellectual property and economic development and growth.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Based on findings from registered SMEs in Kaduna Metropolis, this study concludes that entrepreneurship significantly contributes to economic development in Nigeria. Specifically, entrepreneurial factors, such as risk tolerance, opportunity responsiveness, creativity, and intellectual property (IP) protection, play pivotal roles in driving sustainable growth. Risk tolerance was found to have a positive impact on economic development ($t = 2.925$, $p = 0.046$), supporting Schumpeter's idea of "creative destruction." SMEs that take strategic risks through innovation or expansion tend to create more

jobs and strengthen the economy, highlighting the need for financial tools such as credit guarantees and venture capital. Opportunity responsiveness also showed a significant effect ($t = 3.241$, $p = 0.031$), aligning with Kirzner's theory of entrepreneurial alertness. Agile SMEs that swiftly identify market gaps can enhance their competitiveness, suggesting policy reforms to improve market data access, reduce bureaucratic hurdles, and expand digital infrastructure. Creativity was a critical driver of development ($t = 2.786$, $p = 0.026$), echoing endogenous growth theory. SMEs focused on innovation, whether through new products or technologies, can reduce reliance on oil and lead to structural transformation. Supportive measures, such as research and development (R&D) incentives, innovation hubs, and industry-academia collaboration, are essential. Lastly, intellectual property protection had a strong positive link to economic growth ($t = 3.354$, $p = 0.020$). SMEs with secured IP rights attract more investment and scale innovations faster. However, Nigeria's weak IP enforcement remains a challenge. Drawing lessons from Rwanda's IP reforms, Nigeria must strengthen its legal frameworks and raise awareness among SMEs. In sum, entrepreneurship, especially among SMEs, remains a catalyst for Nigeria's economic transformation. Policymakers and stakeholders must foster an enabling environment that promotes risk-taking, innovation, and IP protection to unlock the sector's full potential.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance the role of entrepreneurship in Nigeria's economic development:

Encourage Risk-Taking Among SMEs: Establish a ₦200 billion National SME Venture Capital Fund to support early-stage businesses in high-growth sectors with long-term financing. A Credit Risk Guarantee Scheme covering 50% of loan defaults should be introduced to boost SME access to credit. Sector-specific business interruption insurance with subsidised premiums (30%) is also recommended. Additionally, entrepreneurship centres should integrate risk management training, including scenario planning and crisis strategies, to improve opportunity responsiveness. They should also create a National Market Intelligence Unit within SMEDAN to deliver real-time market data and alerts via a mobile app. Streamline business registration and licensing into a unified 72-hour digital system to reduce bureaucratic delays. Regional Opportunity Hubs should be developed across the six geopolitical zones to strengthen market linkages. An Export Readiness Program should assist SMEs with trade finance and global market entry. **Promote Creativity and Innovation,** introduce a 150% tax deduction for SME R&D expenses and offer Innovation Vouchers (up to ₦5 million) redeemable at research institutions. Set up at least one Technology Demonstration Centre per state to showcase SME innovations. Launch the Presidential Innovation Awards worth ₦100 million annually and encourage corporate open innovation platforms to involve SMEs in solving industry problems, thereby strengthening Intellectual Property (IP) systems. Establish specialised IP courts in Lagos, Abuja, and Port Harcourt with a 90-day case resolution target. Implement an IP Registration Fast-Track System with 50% fee reductions and a 30-day turnaround. A Blockchain-Based IP Registry should be developed for secure, tamper-proof documentation. SMEDAN should run IP Clinics nationwide for advisory support. Universities and research institutions must set up Technology Transfer Offices with funding tied to performance and there should be improvement in institutional quality so that human development should be enhanced.

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